

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Silvio**FIRST NAME:** Dominic**PROGRAM CODE:** DSDD**COURSE CODE :** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 10

PRINCIPLES OF WRITING: HOW TO BE AN EFFECTIVE ACADEMIC OR PROFESSIONAL WRITER

1) INTRODUCTION

Writing is an important skill to have because it enables clear communication of messages to a larger audience. The importance of writing is far greater as the world is transforming into online or digital transactions as opposed to face-to-face interactions. In academia, writing as well as critical thinking, have been regarded as fundamental to the accomplishment of one's studies. In fact, each discipline has its own writing style which makes it much more interesting. Individuals also have their own idiosyncrasies when it comes to writing. Furthermore, many employers, in their job advertisements, seek graduates who demonstrate excellent writing and critical thinking skills. EUCLID's approach in offering ACA-401D as a mandatory course is critical in making sure that students become effective academic or professional writers. I am impressed with the level of detailed information contained in the ACA-401D coursepack which I believe provides the foundation for effective academic and professional writing.

The introductory 14-minute video is very informative and helpful because it clearly explains how to use EUCLID's templates, the fundamentals of rule of style, the difference between the rule of style and a heading or paragraph style, the difference between long and short citations, the proper use of quotations, the file saving conventions, and so on. ACA-401D indicates the rigorous academic requirements expected from EUCLID's students as we progress in the academic journey and approach the critical components of research paper and dissertation writing. As someone who has been in academia for a while and has

written a few papers and reports, I find that effective academic writing is not easy. By introducing the foundational components of how to master academic or professional writing at the beginning of any program is an asset to EUCLID's high-quality academic driven writing. Hence, to know that the aim of academic writing is to "persuade readers of an idea based on evidence" is critical (EUCLID 2019, 1).

2) THE FUNDAMENTALS OF EFFECTIVE ESSAY WRITING

In my current role as an academic librarian, I have often advised students on the basics of academic essay writing and the significance of it being simple and clear. This is because being simple and clear allows research results to be communicated with clarity and ease. The basics of easy writing component of EUCLID's coursepack has reinforced my own beliefs. In fact, understanding that an essay is supposed to answer or address a question through formulation of thesis statement, clear evidence-based reasoning and argumentation, are crucial to any academic or professional writing (ibid.). Over the past few years, I have written several research papers, policy and procedural papers, and myriad reports. And even though I consider myself to be good in essay writing, I find the coursepack materials to offer some inspirational perspectives on academic writing. More specifically, the provision of "sample correction to papers" to show students how the editing process of written work is done (EUCLID 2019, 36). In the next few paragraphs, I will explain some of the concepts - under the fundamentals of effective essay writing - I find interesting and stimulating while reviewing the coursepack for Period 1.

a) Selecting and Focusing Research Topic

I find the simplicity of EUCLID's guide to starting a research essay as important and informative. The encouragement of students to start work on their projects early, define and understand their research question with specific focus on generating keywords for use in academic databases, and constructing the initial research plan is in point (EUCLID 2019, 1). I have discovered these guides fairly lately in my academic career but have used them considerably. For this reason, selecting and focusing a research question is a key concept that all students and aspiring writers need to develop.

Another aspect I noticed missing in the coursepack is information on how to develop a thesis statement. Although there is a mention of thesis statement, however, the nuts and bolts of how to create or develop one is not provided. Thus, if students could be provided examples on how to develop a thesis statement as well as documentation on what a thesis statement is, would be appreciated.

b) Researching a Topic

In my current role as an academic librarian, it is very easy to evaluate and figure out the difference between a well-researched and a not well-researched paper. I fully

concur that researching, and writing are critical to an effective essay writing (EUCLID 2019, 2). Furthermore, researching does provide the evidenced required to make nuanced defense of viewpoints in a paper. That is, including research papers and data from academic sources validates a writer's position. Moreover, being able to apply both creative and critical thinking is important because both do enhance the production of focused papers (ibid).

What I find missing, in this section from the coursepack, is guidance on how to conduct research and how to develop a research plan. As a researcher, I find it very beneficial having a well-constructed research strategy to guide database and library catalog searches. For instance, the plan should contain information on what to search for first, second, third, et cetera. That is, when to search for books, journal articles, newspaper articles, and web resources in the research lifecycle. Therefore, including examples on how to construct a manageable search strategy would have been helpful.

My previous research steps involved searching for books first because they provide the foundational knowledge or broad overview of the topic, discuss big ideas and place the topic being studied in context with other issues. Furthermore, books take long to be published. As a result, the possibility of a new book on a topic being investigated to be published during the exploration period to the topic is very unlikely. However, journal and newspaper articles, and web resources are published more regularly and should be searched for after books. I know this is still very early in the introductory course, but I hope there is a plan to show students how to research multiple library databases and/or Google Scholar.

c) Academic Integrity/Academic Dishonesty

As noted earlier, I personally embrace the zero-tolerance approach to academic dishonesty/plagiarism taken by EUCLID (EUCLID 2019, 5). In fact, many universities globally consider plagiarism as a serious academic offense. It is not just immoral to plagiarize someone else's work but also a clear indication of academic laziness on the part of the one who plagiarizes. The scholarly and creative research process is not easy. A significant amount of effort and patience is required to write and create a work of an acceptable quality, and to not be accorded the credit one is due is plain unfair and wrong.

Furthermore, it is of a paramount importance that students must understand the principles of academic integrity/plagiarism as they begin to focus their research topic. EUCLID's coursepack has a chapter on plagiarism which I believe is crucial to review adequately before delving into researching a paper. Students should be encouraged to understand University policies regarding plagiarism before even beginning to brainstorm their research topic. That is why I suggest it is critical to include plagiarism as a part of the "starting the essay" section of the coursepack (EUCLID 2019, 1). I find that when students are advised about plagiarism early on, they will try to avoid it. Nevertheless, I fully agree that writers should avoid plagiarism and accord due credit to authors whose works have been sourced (EUCLID 2019, 5). This is very important.

In fact, the issue of plagiarism is not only limited to students. Recently, a number of respectable and renowned journals have retracted many articles because they contain instances of academic dishonesty (Retraction Watch n.d.). The coursepack gives few examples of plagiarism, however, I would add that plagiarism or academic cheating may also take the form of falsifying data in reports, dissertation, and other presentations. Furthermore, it may include attempts to complete, by whatever irregular means, any requirements for a class. There is also self-plagiarism, when an author reuses their work that has been previously published.

I fully appreciate EUCLID's attempt to help students avoid plagiarism by introducing the principles of paraphrasing and giving examples of how to do it (EUCLID 2019, 9). Nevertheless, the onus is on the writer/student to make sure that the information being relayed is an accurate representation of the author's original work (EUCLID 2019, 8). The coursepack and the Turabian style guide are wonderful resources for students to consult to avoid plagiarism because they contain concrete examples of how not to paraphrase, and how to make effective use of quotations and citations (EUCLID 2019, 5-13).

3) NOTABLE OBSERVATIONS

As I thoroughly studied and reviewed the required material for this course, I have noticed a few irregularities that I would like to share. I have realized that the literature review section is actually redundant. Although it is titled as "literature review" the information included in it has nothing to do with literature review per se (EUCLID 2019, 17-23). I hope this was done intentionally for students to figure out. I have also noticed that the section on the procedure for handing in assignments is not relevant because the introductory video provided clear instructions on how to submit assignments (EUCLID 2019).

Furthermore, since EUCLID functions online and uses the Zotero software for bibliographic management, I find the suggestion to "copy down the bibliographic details of everything you read" as odd given the fact that students have been encouraged to highlight texts while reviewing the required course material (EUCLID 2019, 2). The reference to see "The Learning Centre guide Effective Note-making from Written Text" may also be mistakenly left there because the guide is nowhere to be found in the coursepack (ibid).

I have also realized that on pages 6 and 7 of the coursepack, the in-text citation is written as (Gerson and Gerson 146) with no comma (EUCLID 2019, 6-7). However, I consulted the CMS Crib Sheet which confirmed a comma should have been inserted between the author and the page number (EUCLID 2019, 51). Talking about the CMS Crib Sheet, I would like to note that the one included in the coursepack is outdated because it was last revised in Fall 2006 (EUCLID 2019, 44). There is a new version which was last updated in Fall 2007 (Scribe 2007). In terms of book titles, the Turabian style recommends that titles be italicized in the text and references (EUCLID 2019, 47). Nevertheless, in page 7 the title was not italicized. Furthermore, on page 16 there is a recommendation to students

to make appointment with writing tutors assigned to the course in case they are concerned about their writing (EUCLID 2019, 16). Are there writing tutors assigned to this course that I am not aware of? If so, it would be helpful to share the information.

In general, I have also enjoyed reviewing the sections on the difference between American and British English, and the fact that the American English has been influenced by other societal factors, for example, Yiddish and Ethnic Jews, Blacks as well as other cultural factors. Furthermore, I am impressed with the general advise on whether to start a sentence with “And”; when and how to use “well” and “good”; and when to write out a number or use numeral (EUCLID 2019, 21-35). Likewise, the section on the use of Latin abbreviations and expressions in writing was refreshing (EUCLID 2019, 56). I have used some of the abbreviations (e.g., etc., et al., i.e., ibid, N.B, P.S., sic) in my previous writings without proper understanding of their Latin origin.

4) CONCLUSION

Writing is a skill that is learned and can be developed further with individualistic and discipline specific style and idiosyncrasies. As a doctoral student in Sustainable Development and Diplomacy (DSDD) program, I believe the introductory video, and the mandatory material in the ACA-401D Period 1 coursepack, will help me develop and strengthen the writing skills required to complete the program. The course covered a myriad of important topics, including the fundamentals of essay writing, plagiarism, Word styles, difference between American and British English, CMS Crib Sheet, Chicago style and usage, and Latin abbreviations and expressions currently in use in writing. Furthermore, there is significant emphasis and guidance on how to avoid plagiarism through the use of paraphrasing, citations, and quotations. Although, the ACA-401D coursepack is comprehensive, however, I have observed a few notable omissions which I have explained in previous sections. Regardless, this introductory material has whetted my appetite and I am looking forward with anticipation to enjoying ACA-401D Period 2.

REFERENCES

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